

JOURNAL

TITLE

Intelligent Multi-Objective Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (iMO-NMPC):
Towards the ‘on-line’ optimization of highly complex control problems.

AUTHORS

Names and affiliations:

Juan José Valera García^{a, b}

Vicente Gómez Garay^b

Eloy Irigoyen Gordo^b

Fernando Artaza Fano^b

Mikel Larrea Sukia^b

^a Tecnalia Research & Innovation – Industry and Transport Division. Parque Tecnológico de Zamudio, Edificio 202, E-48170, Zamudio, Vizcaya, Spain.

^b University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Intelligent Control Research Group, Department of System Engineering and Automatic Control, ETSI, 48013, Bilbao, Vizcaya, Spain

ABSTRACT

The benefits of using the Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (NMPC) for the response optimization of highly complex controlled plants are well known. Nevertheless the complexity and associated high computational cost make its implementation and reliability the focus of the discussion. This paper proposes an Intelligent and Multi-Objective NMPC (iMO-NMPC) scheme where several, and often conflicting, control objectives can be competing simultaneously in the control problem. In the iMO-NMPC, the combination of a Neural Network, a Multi-Objective Genetic Algorithm and a Fuzzy Inference System, help us in the nonlinear search for near-optimal control actions, aiming to fulfil all the specified control objectives simultaneously. The proposed scheme adds an expert stage that can adaptively change the degree of importance (weight) of each control objective according to the state of the plant. Therefore, once the nonlinear multi-objective optimization problem is solved at each sampling time and the non-inferior control solutions belonging to the set of Pareto are obtained, the most appropriate one is selected by using the control objectives weights inferred from the expert stage. Some experimental results showing the iMO-NMPC effectiveness and the details about its implementation over control systems with low sampling times are also presented and discussed in this paper.

KEYWORDS

Nonlinear Model Predictive Control
Multi-Objective Optimization
NARX Neural Network
Genetic Algorithm
Expert Decision Maker

1.- Introduction

Classical control schemes based on the well-known Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controller are still widely used in process industries. In general, for each controlled variable of the plant, a PID controller is used and tuned to satisfy the control requirements (including disturbances rejection) in the vicinity of its most probable operation point. Therefore, the control requirements can be fulfilled and the behaviour of the variables to be controlled can be stable and robust if the PID controllers are correctly tuned using the linear approach of the plant around its operation point. The main reasons for using the PID controller are among others, its simplicity, easy implementation, low cost, effectiveness, physical meaning and its intuitive tune procedures.

Nowadays, there are strong exigencies and requirements for automatic control processes. Their quality, flexibility, fast response and precision are closely looked at due to the necessity to bring out high added value products in the highly competitive and globalized current markets. In addition, it is well known that the real processes or plants are increasingly complex, falling into high nonlinearities, non-predictive or even instabilities in their responses when linear approaches around one operation point are used for the design and tune of their automatic controllers. In fact, the control complexity is higher when the problem has strongly coupled multiple inputs/outputs and several (often conflicting) control objectives must be fulfilled simultaneously.

A highly complex control problem could be described as a problem in which a stable, robust and optimized response of the plant must be guaranteed for different operation points, and when: (1) The environmental conditions can change, (2) the plant has strongly coupled multiple input and output variables, (3) there is a poor understanding of the plant dynamics and their environment, (4) some variables have a highly nonlinear behaviour, and (5) there are several conflicting control objectives/requirements to be satisfied simultaneously. Since the 1980s, a great deal of interest and research effort has gone into solving these kinds of control problems. Modern control theories and model based control strategies such as, the Adaptive Control [Aström, K.J., & Wittenmark, 1995] and the Model Predictive Control [Clarke, D.W., et All, 1987] [Clarke, D.W., 1988] [García, C., Prett, D., & Morari, M., 1989], were developed and well analyzed. The first advances in the development of microelectronics and digital processors also motivated these theories.

The Adaptive Control classical schemes are usually implemented using linear approaches of the plant dynamic model and the controller. The model parameters (model structure needed to be known a priori) are recursively recalculated by the controller for each different operation point, a linear model approach always being assumed in order to be able to calculate analytically the control action. For instance, the 'on-line' plant dynamic model identification based on Recursive Least Mean Squares methods as well as on stochastic methods and the calculation of the control actions based on the pole placement techniques as well as based on the minimization of a quadratic cost function were very popular [Aström, K.J., & Wittenmark, B., 1995].

On the other hand, the Model Predictive Control (MPC) involves a very interesting control strategy. It integrates optimal control, processes control with dead times, multivariable processes, and it uses future references when they are known in advance. Due to the use of a finite control horizon, it permits the considerations of constraints

and nonlinearities of the controlled plant. In addition, MPC introduces a feed-forward control action and a natural way to reject the measured disturbances thanks to its predictive point of view [Camacho, E. F., & Bordons, C., 2004b]. In the case of MPC initial schemes, linear approaches of the plant models together with quadratic forms of the objective function to be minimized (cost function) are assumed in order to obtain the control actions in an analytical form [Camacho E. F., & Bordons, C., 2004a] [Rawlings, J., 2000].

These initial approaches, however, cannot provide satisfactory results when applied to plants with complex dynamics which are either highly nonlinear or are not fully understood [Karray, F. et All, 2002]. Thus, in order to take into account the nonlinearities of the plants, the Nonlinear Adaptive Control and the Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (NMPC) schemes were considered and have been widely developed since the 1990s [Feng, G., & Lozano, R., 1999] [Qin, S. J., & Badgwell, T.A., 1998]. The use of Neural Networks for the identification and approach of highly nonlinear plant dynamic models opened an important branch in the adaptive and predictive control theories, providing excellent results in solving nonlinear control problems [Narendra, K. S., & Parthasarathy, K., 1990], [Hunt, K. J., et All, 1992], [Polycarpou, M., & Ioannou, P. A., 1991] [Lingji Chen, & Narendra, K. S., 2001]. New schemes and formulations were also created for the NMPC schemes [Camacho E. F., & Bordons, C., 2004a]. Most powerful computational systems and advance numerical techniques are needed for the implementation of these higher computational cost nonlinear strategies.

As you can see in section 2 of this paper, the NMPC strategy applied to a multi-objective and constrained control problem has one main and very difficult problem to solve in practice, which in turn becomes a research challenge. In Multi-objective NMPC a highly complex nonlinear and multi-objective optimization problem has to be solved at each controller sampling time in order to calculate the best control actions for the plant. It is very difficult to calculate the global optimum for this kind of problem analytically and, if possible, it would be computationally intractable. On the other hand, it is well known that the interest and application of some intelligent computational techniques such as Neural Networks [Haykin, S., 2008], Genetic Algorithms [Goldberg, D. E., 1989] and Fuzzy Inference Systems [Mamdani, E.H., 1974] [Zadeh, L. A., 1996] [Klir G. J., & Yuan B., 1995] (all intrinsically nonlinear), is growing in the field of process control [Yong-Zai Lu, 1996] [Chyi-Tsong Chen & Shih-Tein Peng, 1999] [Passino K.M., 2001] [Zilouchian, A., & Jamshidi, M., 2001] [Fleming P. J., & Purshouse, R. C., 2002] [Coelho, L. d. S., et All, 2010] [Yu, W., & Sanchez, E. N., 2009] [Yu, W., 2009] [Javadi-Moghaddam, J. & Bagheri, A., 2010] [Nanayakkara, T., 2010][Majhi, B., & Panda, G., 2010]. With the help of these stochastic and heuristic computational techniques one can approach the multi-objective NMPC problem obtaining near-global optimum control solutions. However, some computational restrictions related to their cost and their memory use should be taken into account.

1.1.- Objective, contribution and organization of the paper

The aim of this paper is to contribute in the advances of the application of multi-objective NMPC for the optimization of highly complex control problems, using the combination of three intelligent computational techniques in the proposed and so-called: Intelligent Multi-Objective Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (iMO-NMPC). In the iMO-NMPC proposed scheme, a Neural Network (NN) approaches the nonlinear plant dynamic model and it is used at each controller sampling time to predict the future

values of the variables to be controlled over a selected horizon. A Multi-Objective Genetic Algorithm (MOGA) is also used at each controller sampling time as the NMPC multi-objective optimization solver, to find the set of Pareto optimal control solutions (non-inferior solutions in a multi-objective competitive context) [Pareto, V., 1896] which minimize all the competing control objectives. Finally, a Fuzzy Inference System (FIS) is used at each controller sampling time as Expert Decision Maker (EDM) to select the best control solution (amongst the Pareto set of non-inferior solutions found by the MOGA) according to the state of the plant. Thus, through the EDM, the decision criterion is not unique and constant but it can be adaptively changed by the controller in function of the current and previous state of the plant. For instance, the degree of importance of the control objectives could be different if there is a major change in the state of the plant due to a disturbance, meaning the decision criteria could be automatically changed by the EDM in order to select a better control solution amongst the ones Pareto set for that situation. Therefore, the expert knowledge of the plant operators can be transferred to the NMPC controller in the form of expert rules which could be later used to infer the control objectives degree of importance while the control process is running.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the Multi-objective Nonlinear Model Predictive Control is introduced and its methods and techniques reviewed. Advanced techniques for solving the multi-objective optimization problem are also presented and reviewed in this section. How the iMO-NMPC proposed scheme works is presented in section 3. In sections 4 and 5 the intelligent computational techniques and procedures used to approach the nonlinear plant dynamic model and to find the predictive control actions are respectively presented. Simulation results applying the iMO-NMPC scheme for the control of a highly nonlinear and strongly coupled bi-objective control problem are presented in Section 6. Conclusion and future works are given in Section 7.

2.- Multi-objective Nonlinear Model Predictive Control and its methods.

MPC is formulated as the repeated solution of a (finite) horizon open-loop optimal control problem subject to plant dynamics and input and state constraints. To incorporate feedback, the optimal open-loop control is implemented only until the next sampling time instant [Allgöwer, F., et All, 2004]. Conceptually and from a practical point of view¹, one can see the model predictive control strategy in a multivariable context as a four stage algorithm:

Stage 1: Preparation of variables: At the sampling/step time k , a vector $Y_{i,p}$ (1) is formed using the current values of the n variables to be controlled (usually obtained by measurements) and their r previous data samples stored on the memory of the controller.

$$Y_{i,p} \quad // \quad i = [1, 2, \dots, n], p = [k - r, k - r - 1, \dots, k] \quad (1)$$

In addition a vector $U_{x,c}$ (2) is formed using some control actions' previous data samples also stored on the memory of the controller.

$$U_{x,c} \quad // \quad x = [1, 2, \dots, m], c = [k - r_c, k - r_c - 1, \dots, k - 1] \quad (2)$$

¹ We use this conceptual notation based in inputs, outputs, and transference functions for better problem understanding instead of the space of states notation that is more appropriate for multivariable process control description.

In vector $U_{x,c}$ (2), m is the number of manipulated variables in the control problem and r_c the number of previous data samples to be used for each one. These vectors will be used below (stage 2) in order to solve an optimal control problem.

Stage 2: Optimal control problem: At the same time k , an optimization problem (3) over a predictive horizon h must be solved. The predictive horizon h is the desired number of steps-ahead from the current sampling time (step k) that will be used in the optimization problem formulation.

Find a control actions' vector $U_{x,y}^*$ (3),

$$U_{x,y}^* \quad // \quad x = [1,2,\dots,m], y = [1,2,\dots,h_c] \quad (3)$$

In the equation (3), m is the number of manipulated variables and h_c the number of steps-ahead from the step k selected for the control horizon ($h_c \leq h$).

Which minimize a vector of cost functions $J_{g,l}$ (4), being $f_{g,l}$ a set of n_f functions that contain the desired control objectives to be minimized.

$$J_{g,l} = f_{g,l}(R_{i,j}, Y_{i,j}^*) \quad // \quad g = [1,2,\dots,n_f], i = [1,2,\dots,n], j = [1,2,\dots,h] \quad (4)$$

In the equation (4), vector $R_{i,j}$ contains the desired values for the n variables to be controlled over the selected predictive horizon h , and vector $Y_{i,j}^*$ contains the predicted values of the n variables to be controlled over h .

Subject to the constrain (5), due to the vector $Y_{i,j}^*$ must satisfy the plant dynamic model approach. In this case NLM is a nonlinear model. This constrain (5) implies that predictions (over h) of the variables to be controlled are needed

$$Y_{i,j}^* = NLM(U_{x,y}^*, U_{x,c}, Y_{i,p}) \quad (5)$$

Other **constrains** related to the variable limits can also be formulated and taken into account in the optimization problem (6), (7). The vectors $ULL_{x,y}$ and $UHL_{x,y}$ contain respectively the low and high value limits of the manipulated variables (control actions), and the vectors $YLL_{i,j}$ and $YHL_{i,j}$ contain the value limits of the variables to be controlled.

$$ULL_{x,y} \leq U_{x,y}^* \leq UHL_{x,y} \quad (6)$$

$$YLL_{i,j} \leq Y_{i,j}^* \leq YHL_{i,j} \quad (7)$$

Usually each cost function (each element of $J_{i,l}$) is formed with the control objectives corresponding to each variable to be controlled (case of $n_f = n$). One of the most common control objectives is the error between the desired and predicted values of the variable to be controlled over h . However, sometimes there are either more cost functions than the number of variables to be controlled ($n_f > n$) or even less cost functions ($n_f < n$) in which the control objectives of some variables are aggregated in one cost function to reduce the optimization problem complexity. One can note the complexity of the optimization problem especially when there is coupling between the variables in the control problem. For instance, some variables to be controlled can be

affected (in an opposite sense) by one element of the control actions' vector. In this case, multiple elements of the cost functions' vector can be in conflict or competing simultaneously.

Stage 3: Control actions calculation: Once the optimization problem is solved and the control actions' vector $U_{x,y}^*$ has been found, the final control actions vector $U_{x,l}$ is obtained by taking the first column of the $U_{x,y}^*$ vector (8).

$$U_{x,l} = U_{x,y}^* \quad \forall y = 1 \quad (8)$$

Stage 4: Control actions are taken out to the plant's manipulated variables and the algorithm goes to stage 1 again to proceed with the next control sampling/step-time.

Usually, linear approaches for the plant dynamic models and quadratic forms for the objective-cost functions are considered in MPC's schemes in order to find an explicit solution of the optimization problem [Camacho, E. F., & Bordons, C., 2004a]. NMPC refers to MPC schemes that are based on nonlinear models and/or they consider non-quadratic cost-function as well as general nonlinear constraints [Allgöwer F., et All, 2004]. Excellent and complete reviews of existing NMPC techniques including their theoretical, computational and implementation aspects can be found in [Mayne, D. Q., et All, 2000] [Allgöwer, F., et All, 1999] [Rawlings, J., 2000] [Morari, M., & Lee, J. H., 1999] [Allgöwer F., et All, 2004] [Camacho, E. F., & Bordons, C., 2004]. NMPC implies the on-line solution of a nonlinear optimal control problem (nonlinear program) at each controller sampling time, which is computationally expensive. In order to analytically find the optimal solution, typically direct optimization methods using a finite parameterization of the problem are used in a receding horizon form [Allgöwer, F., et All, 2004]. Approaches for solving the nonlinear optimization problem can be found in [Biegler, L., & Rawlings, J.B., 1991] [Biegler, L., 2000], where stability analyses were included in these very interesting research works. Different considerations related to efficient NMPC formulations were also created, such as the use of short predictive horizon [Chen, H., & Allgöwer, F., 1998] and especially the use of suboptimal strategies in which feasibility implies stability [Scokaert P. O. M, et All, 1999]. In the case of suboptimal strategies not global minima has to be found, it is sufficient to find a suboptimal solution that causes a decrease in the function cost at each sample time to guarantee stability.

In NMPC schemes the analytical approach when multiple conflicting objectives / function costs have to be minimized simultaneously, taking into account several constraints, is often very difficult to formulate and his solution computationally intractable. In addition, there exists another complex problem related to the nonlinear dynamic model approach used to make the plant outputs predictions. Three kinds of models are usually used to capture the nonlinear dynamics of the plant [Camacho E. F., & Bordons, C., 2004b]: (1) Empirical models (Neural Networks, Volterra Models, NARX, etc.), (2) Fundamental models solving the balance equations and (3) Hybrid models combining the empirical and fundamental approaches. Neural Networks are being used a lot in NMPC schemes, not only for the identification of the plant dynamics but also for the linearization of the optimization problem [Becerra, V., 2005]. Also the denominated Support Vector Regression (SVR) [Cristianini, N. & Shawe-Taylor, J., 2000] has been widely recognized to be effective as a general nonlinear models approach. A review of different techniques and approaches used for solving NMPC,

where formulations such as suboptimal NMPC, feedback linearization, and NMPC based in Neural Networks are described in detail, can be found in [Camacho E. F. & Bordons, C., 2004a].

2.1.- Multi-objective optimization in NMPC schemes

It has already been mentioned in this section that the NMPC formulation requires the ‘on-line’ solution of a constrained nonlinear optimization problem at each controller sampling time. The most complex optimization problems are those that imply the minimization of a nonlinear and non-convex function. Usually, these kinds of problems are solved using either Sequential Quadratic Programming (SQP) [Boggs, P. T., & Tolle, J. W., 1996] [Nocedal, J. N., & Wright, S. J., 1999] or by using nonlinear searching methods as evolutionary algorithms [Michalewicz, Z., Fogel, D.B., 2000]. SQP are extensions of Newton’s type methods to achieve the convergence of the optimization problem to the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker conditions. In each step of this iterative technique, some quadratic approaches and linear constraints are used to solve the nonlinear and non-quadratic problem [Camacho, E. F., & Bordons, C., 2004b]. The nonlinear searching techniques based in evolutionary algorithms are computationally expensive and do not guarantee the convergence to the global minima [Morari, M., & Lee, J. H., 1999], [Camacho, E. F., & Bordons, C., 2004] but they have been widely used in the last decade for solving complex optimization problems employing efficient and fast algorithms. With these nonlinear techniques one can directly use any form of cost function (not only quadratic forms). A comparative study using Genetic Algorithms against the SQP technique for the resolution of constrained and complex optimization problems can be found in [Sheta, A., & Turabieh, H., 2006].

In a multi-objective context, where several conflicting objectives / function costs need to be minimized simultaneously, aggregating all the objectives in a single objective function and minimizing it usually solves the optimization problem. Some application examples using this weighted objective aggregation methodology are shown in [Coello C. A. C, 1999]. The main difficulty of the objective aggregation method resides in the selection of the appropriate weights for each objective on the new aggregated function. The value of these weights can be difficult to obtain due to the fact that the final function cost does not have a physical meaning and it is multi-dimensional. Usually test and error procedures are used in order to obtain the objective weights in the practice. However some authors such as [Messac, A., & Wilson, B. H., 1999], have tried to solve this inconvenience by using the physical knowledge of the problem. In this approach, the weights of each objective are inferred from intuitive rules, which characterize the problem. Thus, one has to define and formulate only the intuitive rules from a physical point of view, see [Messac, A., & Wilson, B. H., 1999]. Another important disadvantage of the objectives aggregation method resides in that only one solution that minimizes the aggregated function cost is obtained. In multi-objective problems where there are conflicting objectives, there can be different solutions, all of them optimal depending on the objective considered. Therefore, if only one function cost with all the objectives aggregated is minimized, richness in the solution can be lost.

In the context of a conflicting multi-objective optimization problem all the optimal solutions obtained, which means that any improvement in one of the objectives makes other objectives worse, are denominated non-inferior solutions and all of them belong to the set of Pareto [Pareto, V., 1896]. There are several methods to search for the non-inferior (set of Pareto) solutions in the multi-objective optimization context. Among

them the ones based on evolutionary algorithms stand out. Excellent research contributions and discussion based on the search of the set of Pareto can be found in [Fonseca, C. M., & Fleming, P. J., 1995] [Coello C.A.C, 1999] [Fleming, P. J., & Purshouse, R.C., 2002] [Deb, K., 2001]. Examples of efficient evolutionary algorithms such as Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm I & II (NSGA) and the Micro-Genetic Algorithm (μ -GA) can be found in [Srinivas N., & Deb., K., 1994] [Deb, K. et All, 2002] and [Toscano, G., & Coello, C. A. C., 2003] respectively. The main inconveniences of these techniques are their high computational cost, the need of a Decision Maker (DM) to select one solution (the best) among the Pareto set, as well as the difficulty of demonstrating the stability, the convergence to a near global optimal and the robustness of the final solution. The last issue to point out is that the techniques used to carry out stability and robustness analysis are based on the denominated Markov's finite chains [Goldberg, D. E., & Segrest, P., 1987].

2.2.- Recent researches in Multi-objective NMPC

In recent years, different multi-objective optimization techniques have been proposed for the use in MPC and NMPC schemes. For instance in [Bemporad A., De la Peña, D.M., 2009], a multi-objective MPC scheme is proposed in which the set of Pareto is searched at each sampling time of the controller. In addition the authors provide conditions for selecting a Pareto solution that is optimal for a desired weighted sum of the different objectives and that preserves the closed-loop asymptotic stability. Multi-parametric multi-objective linear programming and multi-objective quadratic programming were also investigated and used in this scheme where linear assumption of the process model and extensions of linear and quadratic programming techniques are considered.

In [Laabidi, K., et All., 2007], the authors tackle the multi-objective NMPC scheme for a Single Input Single Output (SISO) process with two control objectives. In this work a Neural Network is used for the model dynamic approach of the SISO plant to be controlled, a Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA) [Srinivas, N., & Deb, K., 1994] to search the set of Pareto non-inferior solutions at each sampling time, and a DM with an unique and constant decision criterion based on the minimization of the vector length between the Pareto frontier curve and the origin of coordinates (0, 0) of the Pareto set.

In [Nakayama, H., et All, 2010], the authors propose a multi-objective model predictive optimization method using Support Vector Regression (SVR) for the nonlinear model approach. A satisfying trade-off method [Nakayama, H. & Sawaragi, Y., 1984] is used for multi-objective optimization which is applied along with some meta-heuristic optimization methods such as genetic algorithms. An aspiration level method is used in an interactive way between the multi-objective optimization method and the Decision Maker (DM) in order to obtain the final solution. In this case the decision criterion for the DM is also unique and constant.

3.- iMO-NMPC proposed scheme

The structure and block diagram of the proposed iMO-NMPC scheme is shown in Fig. 1. We will use the same four stage algorithm introduced in section 2 of this paper to explain how it works.

Fig.1. iMO-NMPC structure and block diagram.

Stage 1: At the current process sampling time, step k , a references' vector $R_{i,j}$ (9a) containing the desired reference trajectories over the predictive horizon h corresponding to the n variables to be controlled is composed. In addition, vectors $Y_{i,p}$ (9b) and $U_{x,c}$ (9c) are also composed.

$$R_{i,j} \quad // \quad i = [1,2,\dots,n], j = [1,2,\dots,h] \quad (9a)$$

$$Y_{i,p} \quad // \quad i = [1,2,\dots,n], p = [k-r, k-r-1, \dots, k] \quad (9b)$$

$$U_{x,c} \quad // \quad x = [1,2,\dots,m], c = [k-r_c, k-r_c-1, \dots, k-1] \quad (9c)$$

In these vectors, n is the number of variables to be controlled, m the number of manipulated variables, h is the number of steps-ahead (from step k) selected for the predictive horizon, k is the current sampling / step time, and r and r_c are respectively the number of previous data samples (behind step k) of the controlled and manipulated variables used for the prediction (stage 2 of the algorithm).

Stage 2: At step k , the multi-objective optimization problem (10, 10a, ..., 10f), over the predictive horizon h , is solved by using a NN, a MOGA, and a FIS.

$$\text{Find} \quad U_{x,y}^* \quad // \quad x = [1,2,\dots,m], y = [1,2,\dots,h_c] \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Which Min:} \quad J_{i,1} = f_{i,1}(R_{i,j}, Y_{i,j}^*) \quad // \quad i = [1,2,\dots,n], j = [1,2,\dots,h] \quad (10a)$$

$$\text{Where: } f_{i,1} = \sum_{j=1}^{j=h} \sqrt{(R_{i,j} - Y_{i,j}^*)^2} \quad (10b)$$

$$\text{Subject to: } Y_{i,j}^* = NN(U_{x,y}^*, U_{x,c}, Y_{i,p}) \quad // \quad c = [k - r_c, k - r_c - 1, \dots, k - 1] \quad (10c)$$

$$p = [k - r, k - r - 1, \dots, k]$$

$$\text{And: } ULL_{x,y} \leq U_{x,y}^* \leq UHL_{x,y} \quad (10d)$$

$$\Delta ULL_{t,j} \leq \Delta U_{i,j}^* \leq \Delta UHL_{t,j} \quad (10e)$$

$$YLL_{t,j} \leq Y_{i,j}^* \leq YHL_{t,j} \quad (10f)$$

The constraints related to the value limits of the control actions, the limits of the gradients of the control actions and the limits of the variables to be controlled are respectively presented in (10d), (10e) and (10f).

You can see that in this case there are the same number of cost functions as there are variables to be controlled (one cost function for each variable to be controlled). Each cost function contains at least one term related to the distance (error) between the desired references $R_{i,j}$ and the predicted values $Y_{i,j}^*$ over the predictive horizon h (10b). If other objectives are pursued for the same variable, they should be aggregated to the corresponding cost function. Vector $Y_{i,j}^*$ (10c) is obtained through a NN by using the vectors $Y_{i,p}$ (9b) and $U_{x,c}$ (9c). Details about the topology of the NN used for the prediction can be found in section 4 of this paper.

When the number of manipulated variables is less than the number of variables to be controlled ($m < n$) and/or a coupling between the variables exists (one control action can simultaneously affect several variables to be controlled, even in the opposite way) a multi-objective optimization problem must be solved.

A MOGA is used to solve the multi-objective optimization problem formulated in (10, 10a, ..., 10f). At each sampling time it searches for the non-inferior solutions belonging to the set of Pareto. These non-inferior solutions will be possible candidates for the m control actions corresponding to the m manipulated variables of the plant. A set of s vectors $U_{x,y}^{*Ni}$ (11) is obtained through the MOGA by carrying out a multi-objective evolutionary search. Details about the MOGA searching procedure can be found in section 5.1.

$$U_{x,y}^{*Ni} \quad // \quad Ni = [1, 2, \dots, s], x = [1, 2, \dots, m], y = [1, 2, \dots, h_c] \quad (11)$$

Once the Pareto set of non-inferior control solutions have been obtained, the following questions need to be answered: Which, among the solutions belonging to the set of Pareto, should be selected as the final control action vector $U_{x,y}^*$ for the current sampling time k ? In a multi-objective optimization context, this decision has to be taken by the DM. A FIS based on expert rules has been proposed as the expert DM in the iMO-NMPC scheme. The expert rules associated to the DM, define the degree of importance of each cost function according to the state and knowledge of the plant. Thus, the final control solution will be inferred from the FIS-DM by using their defined Membership Functions (MSF) and their associated expert rules (12). Details of the developed FIS-DM are presented in section 5.2.

$$U_{x,y}^* = FISDM\{U_{x,y}^{*Ni}, MSF, rules(Y_{i,k}, Y_{i,k-1}, \dots, Y_{i,k-d}, U_{x,k}, U_{x,k-1}, \dots, U_{x,k-e})\} \quad (12)$$

Stage 3: Once the optimization problem is solved and the control actions' vector $U_{x,y}^*$ has been found (stage 2), the final control actions vector $U_{x,l}$ is obtained by taking the first column of the $U_{x,y}^*$ vector (13).

Stage 4: Control actions are taken out to the plant's manipulated variables and the algorithm goes to stage 1 again to proceed with the next control sampling / step-time.

4.- Nonlinear Plant dynamic model approach in the iMO-NMPC scheme

In the IMO-NMPC scheme we propose the use of a NARX dynamic Neural Network (Nonlinear autoregressive network with exogenous inputs) for the plant dynamics model approach. The NARX is a recurrent dynamic network with feedback connections enclosing several layers of the network [Beale, M.H, Hagan, et All, 2010]. The NARX model is based on the well known ARX linear model, which is commonly used in time-series modeling and applications where predictions of some variables are needed. Equation for the NARX model approach for the case of a single SISO system is given in (14), where the next value of the output signal $Y(t)$ is based on its r previous values and the r_c previous values of an independent input signal U .

$$Y(t) = f\{(Y(t-1), Y(t-2), \dots, Y(t-r), U(t-1), U(t-2), \dots, U(t-r_c))\} \quad (14)$$

When predictions of signal $Y(t)$ are needed the recurrent notation (15) can be carried out in order to obtain the signal prediction in $k+h$.

$$\begin{aligned} Y^*(k+1) &= f\{(Y(k), Y(k-1), \dots, Y(k-r), U(k), U(k-1), \dots, U(k-r_c))\} \\ Y^*(k+2) &= f\{(Y^*(k+1), Y(k), \dots, Y(k+1-r), U^*(k+1), U(k), \dots, U(k+1-r_c))\} \\ &\vdots \\ Y^*(k+h) &= f\{(Y^*(k+h-1), \dots, Y^*(k+h-1-r), U^*(k+h-1), \dots, U^*(k+h-1-r_c))\} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

One can implement the NARX model approach by using a multilayer feed-forward neural network that makes an approximation of the nonlinear function f . This model approach can be extended to the case of multiple input/output systems (MIMO). The NARX architecture with one hidden layer is shown in Fig.2. In this figure, m is the number of non-feedback inputs, n is the number of feedback inputs, r_c and r are respectively the number of delays used for non-feedback and feedback inputs, S^H is the number of neurons that there are in the hidden layer, S^O is the number of neurons in the output layer, f_1 and f_2 are respectively the transfer functions used in the neurons of the hidden and output layers, and U and Y are respectively the vectors containing the inputs and outputs of the net. Once the NARX is trained and the neuron connection parameters (weights and bias) are obtained, the calculation of net outputs can be done (16).

Fig.2. Multilayer NARX architecture

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{H} &= f_1[(IW \cdot \bar{U}) + (OW \cdot \bar{Y}) + IB] \\ \bar{Y} &= f_2[(LW \cdot \bar{H}) + LB]\end{aligned}\quad (16)$$

In the NARX dynamic model approach, the network outputs are fed back to inputs of a feed-forward NN. Therefore, a dynamic back-propagation algorithm is needed for the net training where the weights and bias connection parameters are obtained. Dynamic back-propagation training algorithm is more complex than the static back-propagation one used for pure static feed-forward nets. Because the true outputs in all the time steps are known in the training examples, we can use them instead of the feed back estimated net outputs. Thus, a static feed forward network can be trained using for instance the well known Levenberg-Marquardt training algorithm [Hagan, M.T., and M. Menhaj, 1994]. After training, the resulting feed-forward neural network is closed loop transformed and used in feedback mode as nonlinear predictor. This neural network architecture and training methodology is known as series-parallel, and it is well explained in [Beale, M.H, et All, 2010]. Therefore, a NARX Neural Network trained with the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm considering the series-parallel architecture is used in the iMO-NMPC proposed scheme in order to approach the nonlinear plant dynamic model making the outputs predictions over the control horizon, see (10c).

Some important aspects have to be taken into account when NARX are used for nonlinear modelling. The NARX parameters selection such as the number of hidden layers and the number of neurons in each hidden layer, the number of delays (r_c) for the inputs, the number of delays (r) for the feedback outputs, and the type of nonlinear transfer functions selected for the neurons, depend on the behaviour and complexity of the nonlinear plant to be approached. A proper training stage with well thought out training samples is mandatory for the correct estimation and prediction of the variables to be controlled. The training must guarantee a net learning with generalization capacity in order to give a reasonable answer when inputs that have never been seen before are presented. Aspects like the over learning when the net is over trained with particular samples must be avoided. Finally, in predictive controllers is necessary to make predictions for more than one time step-ahead. In NMPC, predictions over h steps-ahead are needed, improving the controller performance and process stability when high predictive horizons are selected. Therefore the NARX must learn the dynamic behaviour of the plant for control horizons greater than one. In section 6, an application

example of the IMO-NMPC controller is described in which a NARX is used to approach the plant dynamic model in order to make the plant outputs prediction.

5.- Calculation of the Predictive control actions in the iMO-NMPC scheme.

The calculation of the plant control actions in the iMO-NMPC proposed scheme are made in two stages at each controller sampling time. At the first stage denominated Searching of Non-Inferior solutions (SoNIs), the non-inferior control solutions belonging to the Pareto set are obtained by using a MOGA. At the second stage denominated Expert Decision Maker (EDM), the most appropriate solution (among the Pareto ones) is selected through a FIS according to the current state of the plant. In the next sub-sections these two stages are explained conceptually.

5.1.- Searching for the non-inferior solutions (SoNIs).

A MOGA is used at each controller sampling time in order to solve the multi-objective optimization problem described in section 3 (10a,...,10f). Details about how a Genetic Algorithm searches for near-optimal solutions in an evolutionary way and how a MOGA can find the Pareto set of non-inferior solutions in a multi-objective optimization context can be found in [Goldberg, D. E., 1989] and [Deb, K. 2001] respectively.

The MOGA needs a set of function fitness in order to evaluate the possible solutions (population individuals) at each generation with the objective of minimizing them. In the case of NMPC, the fitness functions use the predictions obtained by the NARX plant dynamics approach. In Fig. 3, the MOGA algorithm stages are presented. It should be seen that a possible solution to be evaluated, also called *individual or chromosome* contains the control action sequences over the selected horizon, as explained in the equation (3) of section 2. The time available for solving the multi-objective optimization problem has to be lower than the controller sampling time, which is sometimes very short for fast dynamic plant behaviours. This limitation causes convergence difficulties on the MOGA searching, in cases such as when the chromosome encodes many control actions, when high predictive control horizons are selected or when there are a high number of objectives to evaluate. The factors that could have a negative influence on the quality of the MOGA searching are:

- The microprocessor used for the implementation of the controller has low computational power.
- The plant to be controlled has a high number of manipulated variables.
- The predictive control horizon selected for the iMO-NMPC controller is high.
- The size of the initial population used for the MOGA searching is high.
- There are many objectives to be evaluated and minimized simultaneously.

In order to mitigate these factors the actions that have been carried out in the iMO-NMPC proposed scheme are listed below:

- Working with a small (as small as possible) size of the initial population size on the MOGA searching at each generation.

- Initialization of the initial population individuals at each sampling time randomly but adding a certain percentage of the non-inferior solutions corresponding to the solution obtained in the preceding sampling time.
- Reduction of the predictive control horizon whilst ensuring the stability of the plant.
- Reduction of the searching space, through the formulation of constrains related to the limitation of both the value and the gradient of the control actions according to the type of actuators used.

Fig.3. Conceptual algorithm of the MOGA searching procedure.

As mentioned before, the MOGA searching is stopped just before the ending of the sampling time, taking as solution the last just before the MOGA interruption. Thus, one cannot be sure that the final set of non-inferior solutions are global minimums. Therefore the method proposed here could be considered as a suboptimal model predictive control strategy [Scokaert P. O. M, et All, 1999]. In the case of suboptimal strategies it is sufficient to find a suboptimal solution that causes a decrease in the function cost at each sample time to ensure the stability of the plant. This aspect has to be taken into account when supervising the stability of the plant in order to take action to improve the convergence and speed of the MOGA searching algorithm when reduction trends for all the control objectives are not obtained.

5.2.- Expert Decision Maker (EDM)

This subsection presents the procedure used to select, among the set of Pareto non-inferior solutions found by the MOGA, the most appropriate one according to the state of the plant. Usually the decision criterion of the DM is unique and constant [Nakayama, H., et All, 2010] [Laabidi, K., et All, 2007]. For instance in [Laabidi, K., et All., 2007] the authors propose a decision criterion based on the selection of the solution that minimizes the vector length between the Pareto frontier curve and the origin of coordinates $(0, 0)$ of the Pareto set in order to minimize all the control objectives simultaneously (see Fig. 4 for an example with two control objectives). In Fig. 4, among the non-inferior solutions, U_3 would be selected because the vector d_3 has the minimum length.

Fig.4. Example of a Pareto Optimal set.

In the iMO-NMPC scheme we propose that the decision criterion could be variable depending on the state in which the plant is. For instance, the degree of importance of the control objectives could be different if the state of the plant changes strongly due to a disturbance. Thus meaning, the decision criteria could be changed by the controller in order to select a better control solution among the ones in the Pareto optimal set for that situation.

The procedure defined and used as DM in the iMO-NMPC scheme is based on an expert rules based FIS-DM. Note that the FIS-DM does not calculate the control action directly, as is usual in fuzzy control, but it selects one among the solutions computed by the MOGA as the most appropriate according to the current state of the plant. Therefore, the FIS expert rules define the importance (weight) that you want to give to each control objective in terms of the state of the plant. For instance, a valid rule for a problem with two conflicting control objectives could be represented as in (17).

If $process_variable1$ is greater than “ $val1$ ” and $process_variable2$ is lower than “ $val2$ ”,
Then
Objective1_weight is equal to 75%
Objective2_weight is equal to 25%

(17)

The type of FIS recommended in the iMO-NMPC scheme is the one based on the well-known Mamdani's fuzzy inference method [Mamdani, E.H., & Assilian, S., 1975] [Zadeh, L.A., 1973]. Mamdani's fuzzy inference method has been widely used in the field of the expert process control and decision systems. Details about it can be found in [Mamdani, E.H. & Assilian, S., 1975] [Mamdani, E.H., 1974]

The algorithm stages of the proposed EDM are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig.5. Expert Decision Maker algorithm stages.

The FIS infers the cost function weight vector CFW^* according to its associated set of Expert Rules (R_i) and Membership Functions (MSF_i), Fig. 5. Each element of the CFW^* vector contains the most appropriate weight of each control objective according to the state of the plant. For instance the CFW^* inferred from the FIS could be $CFW^* = [0.6, 0.4]$ for a control problem with two objectives. For this example the first objective would have a 60% importance (weight) and the second a 40% importance according to the current state of the plant. On the other hand, each non-inferior solution U_i belonging to the set of Pareto has a corresponding $CFW(U_i)$ vector. In order to explain how a non-inferior solution $CFW(U_i)$ vector is calculated we will use as an example the two conflicting cost functions/objectives shown in Fig. 6. First, the non-inferior solutions with the minimum and maximum values of the cost function J_1 are obtained (18). In the case of the example of Fig. 6, these are U_6 and U_7 respectively. In addition, the non-inferior solutions corresponding to the minimum and maximum values of J_2 are also obtained (19), U_7 and U_6 in Fig. 6. Once these non-inferior solutions have been obtained, the CFW vector corresponding to each non-inferior solution U_i can be calculated (20). As an example, the calculation of the $CFW(U_2)$ vector corresponding to the non-inferior solution U_2 is shown in (21).

Fig.6. Example of a Pareto Optimal set with two conflicting objectives.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Min}(J_1) &= J_1(U_6) \\ \text{Max}(J_1) &= J_1(U_1) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Min}(J_2) &= J_2(U_1) \\ \text{Max}(J_2) &= J_2(U_6) \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

$$CFW(U_i) = \left[\frac{\text{Max}(J_1) - J_1(U_i)}{\text{Max}(J_1) - \text{Min}(J_1)}, \frac{\text{Max}(J_2) - J_2(U_i)}{\text{Max}(J_2) - \text{Min}(J_2)} \right] \quad (20)$$

$$CFW(U_2) = \left[\frac{J_1(U_1) - J_1(U_2)}{J_1(U_1) - J_1(U_6)}, \frac{J_2(U_6) - J_2(U_2)}{J_2(U_6) - J_2(U_1)} \right] \quad (21)$$

Once the $CFW(U_i)$ vector is calculated for all the non-inferior solutions (s is the number of non-inferior solutions), the one whose associated CFW vector is closest to the CFW^* vector inferred from the FIS will be selected as the final control solution (22).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Find} \quad & U_i \quad // \quad i = [1, 2, \dots, s] \\ \text{Which Min.} \quad & \text{Error} [CFW^* - CFW(U_i)] \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

6.- Simulation results and discussion

The simulation results obtained applying the iMO-NMPC control scheme over a highly nonlinear and coupled bi-objective control problem are shown in this section. The plant is presented in Fig. 7, in which the variables to be controlled are the position of a transfer car (Y) and the swinging angle of its suspended load (A). One of the control objectives is to bring the transfer-car to a new position as fast as possible minimizing the positioning error and avoiding overshoot at final position. The minimization of the load suspended swinging angle during the positioning is the second control objective.

The suspended load can swing freely around the point $(Y, 0)$ producing the most important nonlinearities in the dynamic model of the plant.

Fig.7. Transfer car with a suspended load. Plant to be controlled with the iMO-NMPC control scheme.

On the control problem, the manipulated variable (u) is the pulse-with-modulation (PWM) index of the electric drive that provides the transfer car motion. The higher the PWM index, the higher the torque provided by the drive. The PWM index can take floating point values under the limits ± 1 , where the sign implies the torque direction in the four quadrant drive space.

It can be seen that it is a control problem with one input and two outputs with a high coupling between them. For instance, the objective of minimizing the transfer-car positioning time will cause higher acceleration, speed and deceleration movements so the swinging angle can increase. On the other hand, a disturbance coming into the plant (a blow or a gust of wind) could cause the suspended load to swing high. Thus when it swings high the controller should react in order to minimize it by changing the control action which will cause a displacement of the transfer car increasing the positioning error.

6.1.- Nonlinear plant modelling approach using a NARX Neural Network

A dynamic NARX net has been used for the nonlinear plant dynamic model approach, Fig 8. The net inputs are the manipulated variable u_k , and the current values (measurements) of the car-transfer position and the swinging angle, Y_k and A_k respectively. Some previous data samples values of u_k , Y_k and A_k were also used as net inputs (four for u_k , Y_k and eight for A_k). The net outputs are the car-transfer position and the swinging angle at the time $k+1$ (Y_{k+1} and A_{k+1}). In the neurons of the output layer a pure linear function has been used. There is a hidden layer with twelve neurons in which the nonlinear function *tangent sigmoid* has been used. Training results using the *Levenberg-Marquardt* algorithm in the series-parallel architecture are shown in Figs. 9-10. It is important to note that in order to test the effectiveness of the trained NARX, the net outputs have been always used (from sampling time $k=8$ to $k=6000$) as feedback inputs so predictions over long horizons are considered.

Fig.8. NARX Neural Network topology for the plant dynamic model approach.

Fig.9. Transfer-car position prediction using the NARX net.

Fig.10. Swinging angle prediction results using the NARX net.

One can see that the NARX plant dynamic model approach works well even with long predictive horizons as is presented in Figs. 9-10.

6.2.- Transfer-car position control results.

Transfer-car position control results applying the iMO-NMPC controller are presented in this subsection. Transfer-car position control (position set point $0.2m$) with a precision more accurate than $\pm 3mm$, no overshoot at the final position, arriving time less than $2s$ and swinging angle less than $\pm 0.05rad$, were the control requirements. Minimization of the position error and the swinging angle were the two control objectives (cost functions) considered.

The controller sampling time was set to $0.01s$ and the selected predictive horizon was $h=8$, so the MOGA chromosome was composed by 8 genes. MOGA population size was set to 50 individuals. At each sampling time the population is initialized randomly but in order to accelerate the MOGA convergence a certain percentage of the best individuals obtained at the preceding sampling time are added. Constraints related with the max-min control action values (PWM index, ± 1), max-min control action gradient values, and max-min values of the variables to be controlled were also applied in order to reduce the searching space. A heuristic crossing function was used in the MOGA searching procedure. Maximum time selected for the MOGA searching was set to $0.01s$, so at this time the searching is interrupted and the last non-inferior individuals just before the interruption are used as solutions at each controller sampling time. A Pareto set of non-inferior solutions obtained at different sampling times while the iMO-NMPC transfer-car position controller is running, are shown in Fig. 11.

Fig.11. Pareto set of non-inferior solutions obtained at different sampling times.

A FIS of Mamdani's type with eight Expert Rules (R_i) was used as EDM. The Memberships Functions (MSF_i) for the inputs (Position error, Swinging Angle error) and for the output (weight for the objective of position error minimization), and the output surface plot according to the MSF_i and the R_i are shown in Fig. 12.

Finally iMO-NMPC transfer-car position controller results are shown in Fig. 13. The transfer-car position control fulfils all the specified requirements.

Fig.12. Member-ship functions of inputs (12a, 12b), output (12c) and output surface (12d) of Mamdani's FIS for the iMO-NMPC EDM.

Fig.13. Transfer-car position control results using the iMO-NMPC controller.

6.3.- Disturbance rejection behaviour.

In this subsection we present the results obtained when a disturbance affects the plant causing a load swinging angle deviation of $0.1rad$. In these conditions, the car must be moved by the iMO-NMPC controller in order to reject the disturbance and reduce the swinging angle to $0rad$. The final position of the car should be the same as it was before the plant was affected by the disturbance. Results are shown in Fig. 14 where one can see the good control performance obtained. At instant $t = 0s$ the initial car position was $0m$ and the swinging angle was forced to be $+0.1rad$. We imposed a maximum car position deviation of $0.02m$ for the swinging angle disturbance rejection. At instant $t = 8s$ the disturbance was rejected and the plant came back to the initial conditions.

Fig.14. Swinging angle disturbance rejection results using the iMO-NMPC controller.

6.3.- Comparison results with a classical PID control.

In order to test the effectiveness of the iMO-NMPC controller we compared it to a classical control scheme based on PID. The plant and the control requirements were the same as used before. Obviously more complex PID control schemes exist such as adaptive or ‘on-line’ self tuning PIDs, but our aim was to explore the advantages of the iMO-NMPC against the most common PID control schemes (tuned for one operation point). In the simulations two PIDs were used, one for the car position control and the other for the swinging angle control. Both PIDs were finely tuned trying to satisfy and improve the control requirements. Comparison results can be seen in Figs. 15-16. One can see that the PID control scheme also satisfies the control requirements but the position control precision is worse than when using the iMO-NMPC controller as is shown in Fig. 16.

The comparison results when a disturbance affects the plant causing a swinging angle of $0.1rad$ are shown in Fig. 17. The PID controllers were tuned according to two criterions. The PIDs first tune criterion was done considering that the car position deviation must be less than $0.02m$ while the swinging angle is being minimized. One can note that the time required to suppress the swinging angle is higher than $15s$, see Fig. 17b. The PIDs second tune criterion was done considering that the swinging angle should be completely suppressed in a time not higher than $8s$ (the same time as iMO-NMPC gets it). With this PID tune criterion the car position deviation while the swinging angle is being suppressed is higher than $0.05m$, see Fig. 17c. One can observe the best response of the iMO-NMPC controller where the swinging angle is completely suppressed in a time not higher than $7s$ with a car position deviation not higher than $0.05m$, see Fig. 17a.

Fig.15. Car position control comparison results using PID and iMO-NMPC.

Fig.16. Car position control comparison results using PID and iMO-NMPC. Precision in the steady-state.

Fig.17. Disturbance rejection comparison results. a) using the iMO-NMPC, b) using PIDs tuned with criterion 1, and c) using PIDs tuned with criterion 2.

7.- Conclusion

In this paper a novel intelligent Multi-Objective Nonlinear Model Predictive Control scheme has been proposed for its application in the 'on-line' optimization of highly complex control problems. The scheme proposed belongs to the sub-optimal NMPC strategies where near-optimal instead of global optimal control solutions are obtained at each control sampling time. The complexity of NMPC implementation for highly nonlinear and multi-objective control problems is very high due to a non-quadratic and non-convex multi-objective optimization problem needs to be solved at each sampling time. In the iMO-NMPC scheme, the combination of some intelligent computational techniques such as Neural Networks, Genetic Algorithms and Fuzzy Inference Systems, help us in the NMPC implementation and application over complex control problems where all the specified control objectives and requirements must be fulfilled simultaneously.

In the iMO-NMPC scheme, a NARX that approaches the nonlinear plant dynamic model is used as plant outputs predictor, a MOGA is used as multi-objective optimization solver in order to obtain the Pareto set of optimal (non-inferior) control solutions at each sampling time, and a FIS is used as Expert Decision Maker for the selection of the most appropriate control solution (among the ones belonging to the set of Pareto) according to the state of the plant. Through the proposed EDM (based on a FIS of Mamdani's type), the decision criterion is not unique and constant but it can be adaptively changed by the controller while the process is running. Therefore, the expert knowledge of the plant operators can be transferred to the iMO-NMPC controller in the form of expert rules defining the degree of importance of the conflicting control objectives in function of the state of the plant.

Formulation, methods and algorithms of the iMO-NMPC controller have been presented in detail including some recommendations to accelerate the MOGA searching convergence. The formulation of some constraints reduces the searching space and the pre-initialization of the MOGA population at each control sampling time in an elitist way, makes the MOGA search of the set of non-inferior solutions faster.

Finally, the results obtained by the simulation of a fast, nonlinear and high coupled bi-objective control problem have tested the iMO-NMPC performance and effectiveness. Advantages and better control performances against the PID common scheme especially in non-normal plant operation conditions have been shown and discussed. A predictive control horizon of eight samples with a controller sampling time of $0.01s$ has been used in the simulations where the plant was well controlled with all the control objectives satisfied simultaneously. A selection of higher predictive horizons and/or a requirement to work with lower controller sampling times makes the MOGA convergence more critical and the quality of the control lower, so in that situation instabilities may appear on the plant. Therefore, improvements in the MOGA solver or the use of faster evolutionary techniques would be needed in order to control systems where longer predictive horizons and/or very low controller sampling times are needed.

Future works and actions will be related to the implementation of the iMO-NMPC controller over a Real Time Embedded System (RTES) where some computational power and memory resource restrictions exist. Also the consideration of the 'on-line' NARX net learning while the process is running will be investigated in order to add an adaptive stage to the iMO-NMPC controller. The application in the field of the Energy

Management Systems & Strategies for Range Extended Electric Vehicles will be the final objective of the intelligent, multi-objective and nonlinear model predictive controller proposed in this work.

Acknowledgement

This work comes under the framework of two research projects. The first titled 'Networked Clean Vehicles 2015 (NCV2015)', with reference IAP-560410- 2008- 40, is being granted by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (National Applied Research Program).

The University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU) granted the second, titled 'Implementation/Integration of Intelligent Control Techniques on Real Time Control Systems – ATICTA-2' with reference S-PE10UN70.

References

- Allgöwer, F., Badgwell, T., Qin, J., Rawlings, J., & Wright, S. (1999). Nonlinear Predictive Control and Moving Horizon Estimation: An Introductory Overview. In P. Frank (Eds.), *Advances in Control, Highlights of ECC'99* (pp. 391-449). Springer Verlag.
- Allgöwer, F., Findeisen R., & Nagy, Z. K. (2004). Nonlinear Model Predictive Control: From Theory to Application. *J. Chin. Inst. Chem. Engrs.*, 35(3), 299-315.
- Aström, K. J., & Wittenmark, B. (1995). *Adaptive Control*. (2nd ed.). Prentice-Hall.
- Beale, M. H., Hagan T.M., & Demuth, H. B. (2010). *Neural Network Toolbox™ User's guide revised for version 7*. The Mathworks, Inc.
- Becerra, V. (2005). Predictive Control of Non Linear Systems using Feedback Linearization Based on Dynamic Neural Networks. *GR/R64193/01 Review Report*. The University of Reading: Department of Cybernetics.
- Bemporad A., & De la Peña, D.M. (2009). Multiobjective model predictive control. *Automatica*, 45(12), 2823-2830.
- Biegler, L. (2000). Efficient Solution of Dynamic Optimization and NMPC Problems. In F. Allgöwer & A. Zheng (Eds.), *Nonlinear Predictive Control* (pp. 219-245). Birkhäuser Basel.
- Biegler, L., & Rawlings, J. B. (1991). Optimization Approaches to Nonlinear Model Predictive Control. In W. Ray & Y. Arkun (Eds.), *Proc. 4th International Conference on Chemical Process Control-CPC IV* (pp. 543-571). AIChE CACHE.
- Boggs, P. T., & Tolle, J.W. (1996). Sequential Quadratic Programming. *Acta numerica*, 4, 1-50.
- Camacho, E. F., & Bordons, C. (2004a). *Model Predictive Control*, (2nd ed.). Springer Verlag.

- Camacho, E. F., & Bordons, C. (2004b). Control Predictivo: Pasado, presente y futuro. *Revista Iberoamericana de Automática e Informática Industrial*, 1(3), 5-28.
- Chen, H., & Allgöwer, F. (1998). A quasi-infinite horizon nonlinear model predictive control scheme with guaranteed stability. *Automatica*, 34(10), 1205-1218.
- Chyi-Tsong Chen, & Shih-Tein Peng (1999). Intelligent process control using neural fuzzy techniques. *Journal of Process Control*, 9(6), 493-503.
- Clarke, D.W., Mohtadi, C., & Tuffs, P.S. (1987). Generalized Predictive Control. Part I. The Basic Algorithm. *Automatica*, 23(2), 137-148.
- Clarke, D.W. (1988). Application of Generalized Predictive Control to Industrial Processes. *IEEE Control Systems Magazine*, 122, 49-55.
- Coelho, L. d. S., Pessoa, M. W., Rodrigues Sumar, R. & Augusto Rodrigues Coelho, A. (2010). Model-free adaptive control design using evolutionary-neural compensator. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 37(1), 499-508.
- Coello, C.A.C. (1999). A Comprehensive Survey of Evolutionary-Based Multiobjective Optimization. *Knowledge and Information Systems*, 1(3), 269-308.
- Cristianini, N. & Shawe-Taylor, J. (2000). *An Introduction to Support Vector Machines and Other Kernel-based Learning Methods*. Cambridge University Press.
- Deb, K. (2001). *Multi-Objective Optimization using Evolutionary Algorithms*. England: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.
- Deb, K., Pratap, A., Agarwal, S. & Meyarivan, T. (2002). A Fast and Elitist Multi-Objective Genetic Algorithm: NSGA-II. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, 6(2), 182-187.
- Feng, G., & Lozano, R. (1999). *Adaptive Control Systems*. Newnes. Elsevier Ltd.
- Fleming P. J., & Purshouse, R. C. (2002). Evolutionary algorithms in control Systems engineering: a survey. *Control Eng. Practice*, 10, 1223-1241
- Fonseca, C. M. & Fleming, P. J. (1995). An Overview of Evolutionary Algorithms in Multiobjective Optimization. *Evolutionary Computation*, 3(1), 1-16.
- García, C. E., Prett, D. M., & Morari, M. (1989). Model Predictive Control: Theory and Practice - A Survey. *Automatica*, 25(3), 335.
- Goldberg, D. E. (1989). *Genetic Algorithms in Search, Optimization, and Machine Learning*. Reading MA: Addison-Wesley.
- Goldberg D. E. & Segrest, P. (1987). *Finite markov chain analysis of genetic algorithms*. In J.J.. Grefenstette (ed.), *Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Genetic Algorithms* (pp. 1-8). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.

- Hagan, M. T., & Menhaj, M. (1994). Training feed-forward networks with the Marquardt algorithm. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, 5(6), 989–993.
- Haykin, S. (2008). *Neural Networks and Learning Machines*. (3rd ed.). Prentice Hall.
- Hunt, K. J., Sbarbaro, D., Bikowski R., & Gawthrop, P. J. (1992). Neural networks for control systems—A survey. *Automatica*, 28(6), 1083-1112.
- Javadi-Moghaddam, J. & Bagheri, A. (2010). An adaptive neuro-fuzzy sliding mode based genetic algorithm control system for under water remotely operated vehicle. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 37(1), 647-660.
- Karray, F., Gueaieb, W., & Al-Sharhan, S. (2002). The hierarchical expert tuning of PID controllers using tools of soft computing. *IEEE Transactions on Systems Man, and Cybernetics, – Part B: Cybernetics*, 32(1), 77–90.
- Klir G. J., & Yuan B. (1995). *Fuzzy Sets and Fuzzy Logic: Theory and Applications*. (1st ed.). Prentice Hall.
- Laabidi, H., Bouani, F., & Ksouri, M. (2007). Multi-criteria optimization in nonlinear predictive control. *Mathematics and Computers in Simulation*, 76(5/6), 363-374.
- Lingji Chen, & Narendra, K. S. (2001). Nonlinear adaptive control using neural networks and multiple models. *Automatica*, 37(8), 1245-1255.
- Majhi, B., & Panda, G. (2010). Development of efficient identification scheme for nonlinear dynamic systems using swarm intelligence techniques. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 37(1), 556-566.
- Mamdani, E.H. (1974). Applications of fuzzy algorithms for control of simple dynamic plant. *Proc. Inst. Elect. Eng.*, 121, 1585–1588.
- Mamdani, E.H. & Assilian, S. (1975). An experiment in linguistic synthesis with a fuzzy logic controller. *International Journal of Man-Machine Studies*, 7(1), 1-13.
- Mayne, D. Q., Rawlings, J. B., Rao, C. V., & Scokaert, P. O. M. (2000). Constrained Model Predictive Control: Stability and Optimality. *Automatica*, 26(6), 789-814.
- Messac A. & Wilson, B. H. (1999). Physical programming for computational control. *AIAA Journal* 36(1), 219-226.
- Michalewicz, Z., Fogel, D. B. (2000). *How to Solve It*. EE.UU.: Springer Verlag.
- Morari, M. (1994). *Advances in Model-Based Predictive Control*. Oxford University Press.
- Morari, M. & Lee, J. H. (1999). Model Predictive Control: Past, Present, and Future. *Comput. Chem. Eng.*, 23(4/5), 667.

- Nakayama, H. & Sawaragi, Y. (1984). Satisficing Trade-off Method for Multiobjective Programming, Interactive Decision Analysis. In M. Grauer & A. Wierzbicki (Eds.), *Proceedings of an International Workshop on Interactive Decision Analysis and Interpretative Computer Intelligence* (pp. 113-122). New York: Springer Verlag.
- Nakayama, H., Yun, Y., & Shirakawa, M., 2010. Multi-objective Model Predictive Control. *Multiple Criteria Decision Making for Sustainable Energy and Transportation Systems, Lecture Notes in Economics and Mathematical Systems, 634* (pp. 277-287). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Nanayakkara, T. (2010). Intelligent Control Systems with an Introduction to System of Systems Engineering. *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine, 17*(2), 108-109.
- Narendra, K. S., & Parthasarathy, K. (1990). Identification and control of dynamic systems using neural networks. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks, 1*(1), 4-27.
- Narendra, K. S., & Mukhopadhyay, S. (1997). Adaptive control using neural networks and approximate models. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks, 8*(3), 475-485.
- Nocedal, J. N., & Wright, S. J. (1999). *Numerical Optimization*. Prentice Hall, (Chapters 12, 18).
- Pareto, V. (1896). *Cours D'Economic Politique, volume I and II*. F. Rouge, Laussane.
- Passino, K. M. (2001). Intelligent Control: An Overview of Techniques. In T. Samad (Eds.), *Perspectives in Control: New Concepts and Applications*. New Jersey: IEEE Press.
- Polycarpou, M. M., & Ioannou, P. A. (1991). Identification and control of nonlinear systems using neural network models: Design and stability analysis. *Report 91-09-01, Electrical Engineering-Systems*. University of Southern California.
- Qin, S.J., & Badgwell, T.A. (1998). An Overview of Nonlinear Model Predictive Control Applications. In IFAC Workshop on Nonlinear Model Predictive Control. *Assesment and Future Directions*. Switzerland: Ascona.
- Rawlings, J. (2000). Tutorial Overview of Model Predictive Control. *IEEE Control Systems Magazine, 20*, 38-52.
- Scokaert, P.O.M., Mayne, D.Q., Rawlings, J. B. (1999). Suboptimal model predictive control (feasibility implies stability). *IEEE transaction on automatic control, 44*(3), 648-654.
- Sheta A., & Turabieh, H. (2006). A Comparison between Genetic Algorithms and Sequential Quadratic in Solving Constrained Optimization Problems. *International Journal on Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AIML), 6*(1), 67-74.
- Srinivas N., & Deb., K. (1994). Multiobjective Optimization Using Non-dominated Sorting in Genetic Algorithms. *Evolutionary Computation, 2*(3), 221-248.

Toscano, G., & Coello, C. A. (2003). The microgenetic algorithm 2: Towards on-line adaptation in evolutionary multiobjective optimization. *Evolutionary Multi-Criterion Optimization. Second International Conference EMO 2003*, 2632, 252-266.

Yong-Zai Lu (1996). *Industrial Intelligent Control: Fundamental and Applications*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.

Yu, W., & Sanchez, E. N. (2009). *Advances in Computational Intelligence*. Springer Verlag.

Yu, W. (2009). *Recent Advances in Intelligent Control Systems*. Springer Verlag.

Zadeh, L.A. (1973). Outline of a new approach to the analysis of complex systems and decision processes. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics*, 3(1), 28-44.

Zadeh, L. A. (1996). Fuzzy Sets, Fuzzy Logic, Fuzzy Systems: Selected papers by Lotfi A. Zadeh. In G. J. Klir & B. Yuan (Eds.), *Advances in Fuzzy Systems – Applications and Theory Vol. 6*. NJ: World Scientific Press.

Zilouchian, A., & Jamshidi, M. (2001). *Intelligent Control Systems Using Soft Computing Methodologies*. (1st ed.). CRC Press.